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Predicting the Impact of Climate Change on Water Resources in the Me River Basin Using the Average of Three Climate Models to Assess the Water Balance by 2050

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Abstract

Water resources in the Mé river basin in south-eastern Côte d'Ivoire are strongly influenced by seasonal and interannual rainfall variability, which affects groundwater recharge and the sustainability of river flows. In this difficult context of water availability, the Mé River, which drains this basin, has been selected to address the drinking water supply problems of the city of Abidjan, whose population is growing rapidly. In view of this situation, we have opted to assess the future impacts of climate change on the Mé's water resources in order to simulate flows and evaluate its water stocks by 2050. To achieve this, we used daily precipitation and temperature data from Regional Climate Models derived from GCMs (CNRM-CM5, EC-EARTH and MPI-ESM-LR) under RCP (Representative Concentration Pathway) scenarios RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5, corrected respectively by the quantile-quantile method and the linear scaling method, were used to predict flows by 2050. The model was calibrated and evaluated using data from the 2016-2018 and 2019-2022 time series, precipitation, evapotranspiration and flow rates collected in the basin. The results of the GR4J model simulation gave satisfactory Nash values with 83.1% in calibration and 77% in validation. The various water flows evaluated gave an average rainfall (P) of approximately 1,800 mm over the period 2016-2022: evapotranspiration = 64% of P; runoff = 24% of P and infiltration = 12%. At the end of the hydrological balance, approximately 173,404 m³ constitutes the water stock available for abstraction by the city of Abidjan. The results of the RCM simulations indicate not only an increase in future temperature of between 0.85°C and 1.25°C by 2050, but also an increase in precipitation of 7.4% (CRNM), 0.96% (MPI) and 0.77% (ENSEMBLE) according to the RCP4.5 scenarios, and 3.43%, 0.24% and 0.98% according to the RCP 8.5 scenario, respectively. The EC-EARTH model predicts a 3.04% decrease in average annual precipitation according to RCP 4.5 and a 0.52% increase according to RCP 8.5. In contrast to precipitation, the annual flow of the Mé River is projected to decrease by an average of 65.35% under RCP 4.5 and 71% under RCP 8.5. The scenarios also predict a decrease in the seasonal flow of the Mé River of 28% during the dry season (December to April) and 77% during the wet season (July to May) according to the RCP 4.5 scenario. According to the RCP 8.5 scenario, a decrease in flow of 35% during the dry season and 85% during the wet season is expected. However, flow is expected to increase by more than 60% in September- y (dry season) and by more than 20% in November (wet season) by 2050.

Keywords: Climate change, water resources, GR4J model, Ivory Coast

1. Introduction

Water is a limited and vulnerable resource that is essential to life, socio-economic development and the environment (Yao et al, 2021). Ensuring sufficient access to good quality water for populations is a real challenge for the scientific community (Anzoumanan et al., 2019). It is therefore essential to mobilise a significant source of surface water to meet the water needs of this population. However, climate change associated with global warming caused by increased greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere has caused significant disruption to elements of the hydrological cycle in recent decades, particularly precipitation, evaporation and temperature (Xu et al, 2005; Elsner et al, 2010; Xu et al, 2012; Kundzewicz et al, 2013; Wang et al, 2017). These fluctuations in climatic parameters due to climate change (Kpan, 2017; Keita et al., 2022) are leading to a decrease in water resources in West Africa (Paturel et al., 1997, Servat et al., 1998, Larwanou 2011, Kouakou et al., 2012; Koffi et al 2014). The decline in rainfall has led to a significant drop in the flow of major rivers such as the Senegal River, the Ouémé in Benin and the Bani in Mali (Dao, 2013). These climate change issues, manifested by declining rainfall, rising temperatures and decreasing relative humidity since the 1960s, have been the subject of an extensive scientific research programme in Côte d'Ivoire (Goula et al, 2006). Currently, the water needs of the Ivorian population have increased, particularly in the autonomous district of Abidjan. There is a deficit of 58 million m³per year (Koffi et al., 2017). In response to this situation, the Ivorian authorities have identified surface water sources such as the Aghien lagoon, the Comoé River, etc. (Koffi et al., 2014) to supply the city of Abidjan. There is also the Bonoua aquifer, located 35 km from Abidjan, which has been in operation since 2 March 2015 to strengthen the drinking water supply in southern Abidjan (Ake et al., 2018). According to the National Office for Technical Studies and Development (BNETD), water needs in 2030 are estimated to be double the current estimates. It is therefore clear that needs in 2025 will not be met. This is why; in order to meet the drinking water needs of the population of Abidjan, the Ivorian government has been undertaking a series of measures since 2009 to alleviate the drinking water shortage in the Ivorian economic capital. With a view to resolving the problem of drinking water supply in the city of Abidjan, the Mé project was launched in February 2018 and entrusted to the PFO Africa and Veolia group. This project aims to strengthen the drinking water supply in the country's economic capital by producing an additional 240,000 m³/day from the Mé River. However, this resource could be affected by climate change, which influences the water balance by altering evapotranspiration rates, temperature and precipitation (Kouassi et al., 2019, Abdelkrim, 2013). This is why it is essential to understand the effects of climate change on the future quantitative availability of the river. Several authors (Karambiri & Garc, 2011; Ange-lina et al, 2015; Yira, 2016; Sylla & Nina, 2016, Aziz, 2017; Boko et al., 2020) have found the to be a good tool for studying the impact of climate change in West Africa, the MCR/MCG. This approach to the use of climate models has been demonstrated in the Buyo (Koua, 2014) and Taabo (Anoh, 2014) basins. The

main objective of this work is to assess the future impact of change on the Mé water resource in order to simulate flows and assess its water stocks using the hydrological balance over the period 2041-2060.

2. Presentation of the study area

Covering an area of 4,140 km², the Mé river basin is located in the south-east of Côte d'Ivoire between latitudes 5°30' and 6°20' North and longitudes 3°30' and 4°10' West. It is subject to a transitional equatorial climate characterised by two rainy seasons and two dry seasons, with dense forest vegetation. According to the RGPH (2021), the population is estimated at 726,665 inhabitants. Agriculture is one of the main occupations of the population, with crops such as rubber, cassava, bananas, oil palms and cocoa. The hydrographic network shows that the main watercourse, 140 km long, runs north-south. It also receives water from the Mafou (main tributary) (Ahoussi, 2021). It is drained by the Mé River, which flows into the Aghien Lagoon.

Figure 1 : Geographic presentation of the Mé watershed

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Material

3.1.1 Ground data and climate models

The data used consists of two groups. Data from Regional Climate Models (RCMs) derived from GCMs (CNRM-CM5, EC-EARTH and MPI-ESM-LR) and their "ENSEMBLE" average within the framework of RCP (Representative Concentration Pathway) scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. These RCMs were simulated at a spatial resolution of 50 km (0.44° x 0.44°). The hydro-climatic data consist of daily precipitation, evapotranspiration (ETP) and flow records for the period 2016-2022.

All rainfall data was obtained from the Société d'Exploitation et de Développement Aéroportuaire, Aéronautique et Météorologique (SODEXAM), with the exception of data collected at the Azaguié station installed as part of the Aghien project. Flow data were obtained by converting water levels measured at the Mé bridge limnigraphic station. Finally, to simulate future runoff in the watershed, the ETR and average precipitation for all MCRs over the 2041-2060 period from the model outputs were used. The characteristics of all these data are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Characteristics of the study data

Periods	Stations		
	Limnigraph	Rain gauge	Climate
2016-2022	Bridge Me	Alépé, Brofodoumé, Anyama, Adzopé, Azaguié	Achokoi CET
1986-2005		Azaguie	

Table 2 : Regional Climate Models (RCM) selected for climate projections

MCG	Institution	RCM	Reference
CNRM-ARPEGE	CNRM. France	RCA4 (CNRM-CM5)	(Déqué, 2010)
MPI-ESM-LR	Max-Planck institut for Meteorology. Germany	RCA4 (MPI-ESM-LR)	(Jacob et al., 2007)
EC-EARTH	European consortium (multiple)	RCA4 (EC-EARTH)	(Baker et Huang, 2013)

3.2 Methodology

Step 1: In general, regionalised projections cannot be used directly as input into the hydrological model, due to two main problems: they are biased compared to observations and their spatial scale is too coarse for certain applications. Consequently, a statistical downscaling method is used. The quantile-quantile method and the linear scaling method are used for precipitation and daily temperature, respectively, to generate maximum and minimum precipitation and temperature data for the reference period (1986-2005) and the future period (2041-2060) for the CNRM-CM5, EC-EARTH, MPI-ESM-LR models and their average (ENSEMBLE) under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. As a result, daily precipitation and maximum and minimum temperature data for the periods 1986-2005 and 2041-2060 will have been generated and will be ready for use.

Step 2: Calibration and validation of the GR4J hydrological model will be carried out to obtain the optimal model parameters for the Mé river basin. Daily runoff data from the limnigraphic station at the Mé bridge will be used for calibration and validation.

The calibration period runs from 2016 to 2018 and the validation period from 2019 to 2022.

Step 3: Use the results from step 1 and the model parameters from step 2 as inputs in GR4J to generate 20 years of daily runoff data based on the average of the models under the RCP4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios.

3.2.1 Bias correction methods

3.2.1.1 Evaluation of climate model performance

The performance of the models in reproducing the two climate parameters (observed temperature and precipitation) was evaluated using the bias method (Sabrina, 2015). This method consists of estimating the difference between the simulated and observed data compared to those observed during the 1986-2005 reference period. It is therefore a "relative difference". It allows the difference between simulated precipitation and temperatures during observations to be assessed. Several approaches can be used to assess bias. These include graphical methods, residuals, ranges of variation and statistical methods. We opted for the graphical approach because it highlights the difference in the deviation of the parameters studied.

3.2.1.2 Correction of biases in daily rainfall data: quantile-quantile method

It allows the correction of biases in daily rainfall data simulated by MCRs from observed daily rainfall quantiles. It is much more appropriate for the correction of daily rainfall data which are characterized by high temporal variability (possibility of a difference of more than 100 mm between two consecutive days) and spatial variability (Lebel et al., 1998; Ali et al., 2003).

According to Ibrahim (2012), its implementation on a monthly scale promotes compliance with the seasonal rainfall regime. In this study, the first step is to establish equality between the observed monthly average accumulations and the simulated average accumulations over the reference period.

Generally speaking, the relationship gives:

$$\bar{P}_m^k = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^{Nm} P_{m,i}^k \quad (1)$$

With: N: Number of years in the reference period

Nm: Total number of rainy days in month m over the reference period

\bar{P}_m^k : Mean monthly rainfall of month m for a given scenario and a data series k (observed, simulated), with $m \in [1; 12]$

$P_{m,i}^k$: Height of the ith rainfall of the ordered series of month m of a series k.

However, some comparative studies of simulated and observed daily rainfall data have shown that RCMs have a significant number of low rainfall events and generate very high extreme rainfall events (Frei et al., 2006; Ibrahim, 2012; Fowe, 2015). The number of rainfall events simulated by RCMs is greater than the number of observed rainfall events. Thus, for, $N_m^{sim} > N_m^{Obs}$, the number of rainfall events simulated by RCMs is reduced by $N_{min} = N_m^{sim} - N_m^{Obs}$, and corrects the rainfall amounts whose rank in the ranking is greater than N_{min} ($i > N_{min}$). The rainfall amounts whose rank

in the ranking is less than N_{min} are considered as zero. We note P_m , min the rain value corresponding to rank N_{min} , - Thus for the reference period (1986-2005), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} Si P_{mi}^{sim} < P_{m,min}; \quad P_{m,i}^{sim}(corrigé) \\ = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} Si P_{mi}^{sim} > P_{m,min}; \quad P_{m,i}^{sim}(corrigé) = P_{m,i}^{sim} + \Delta_{m,i} \text{ avec } \Delta_{m,i} \\ = P_{m,i}^{obs} - P_{m,i}^{sim} \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

- For the future period, the minimum threshold is P_m , min and the previous formula is applied to any rainfall whose height is less than or equal to the height of the maximum rainfall of the MCR over the reference period. $P_{m,max}^{sim,ref}$

$$\text{Pour, } P_{mi}^{sim} > P_{m,max}^{sim,ref}, \quad P_{m,i}^{sim}(corrigé) = \frac{P_{m,i}^{sim}}{P_{m,max}^{sim,ref}} \times P_{m,max}^{sim,ref}(corrigé) \quad (4)$$

3.2.1.3 Correction of daily temperature biases: linear scaling method.

There are different scaling methods, but the one chosen in this study is the one established by Fang et al. (2015). It is very similar to the delta method. Although simple in its formulation and implementation, this approach is suitable in temperature correction and its performance has been proven (Sarr et al., 2015; Kabore et al., 2015; N'Tcha, 2018 and Koné, 2023). It consists of taking the difference between the simulated monthly mean temperature and the monthly mean temperature variation rate

It is expressed as follows:

$$T_{m,i}^{cor} = T_{m,i}^{sim} - \Delta T_m \quad (5)$$

With :

ΔT_m : Monthly average temperature change rate $\Delta T_m = \bar{T}_m^{obs} - \bar{T}_m^{sim}$

$T_{m,i}^{cor}$, $T_{m,i}^{sim}$: Corrected daily values and simulated raw temperature of day i of month m .

\bar{T}_m^{obs} , \bar{T}_m^{sim} : Observed and simulated monthly mean values of month m .

The parameter to be corrected is increased by the difference between the observed and simulated monthly mean value by the MCRs during the reference period month by month. This type of correction consists of moving the entire distribution by an identical correction factor for each month m .

3.2.2 Hydrological modelling

In this study, the GR4J hydrological model (Perrin et al. 2003 version) was used to simulate the daily flow of the Mé basin. The GR4J model is a global, empirical model that is robust enough for the transformation of rainfall into flow (Anshuman et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021; Chiew et al., 2022) using two (02) reservoirs: production and routing. Since its

development by CEMAGREF (1980), it has been successively improved by Edijatno (1991), Oudin et al. (2005) and Perrin et al. (2003) and applied by numerous researchers such as (Ruelland et al., 2010; Kunnath-Poovakka and Eldho, 2019; Zeng et al., 2019; Kodja et al., 2020; Zafari et al., 2022) in various climatic regions. The simulation of flows from the GR4J model involves four (04) parameters:

- X1: production reservoir capacity (mm);
- X2: underground exchange coefficient (mm);
- X3: one-day capacity of the routing reservoir (mm);
- X4: base time of the HU1 unit hydrograph (j).

The methodology used for hydrological modelling of the basin is explained with a presentation of the operating diagram of the GR4J model, which can be run in Microsoft Excel. The GR4J hydrological model uses daily precipitation (P) and potential evapotranspiration (PET) as inputs variables and produces daily flow as output. The performance of the model during the calibration phase is evaluated using the Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency coefficient (Nash and Sutcliffe, 1970). The model operates in several successive stages. First, the comparison between precipitation (P) and evapotranspiration (E) determines either net precipitation (Pn) when $P > E$, or net evapotranspiration (En) in the opposite case. Secondly, depending on the level of water storage (S) in the production reservoir, part of the net precipitation (Ps) feeds into this reservoir, causing a variation in S, while the remaining fraction ($Pn - Ps$) generates rapid runoff. This fraction is then added to the percolation (Perc) from the production reservoir to form the total flow Pr. Thirdly, 90% of the flow Pr is transferred through a unit hydrograph UH1 and then routed via a non-linear reservoir, depending on the storage (R) of the routing reservoir, in order to produce the slow flow (Qr). The remaining 10% of Pr is conveyed by a second unit hydrograph (UH2) and constitutes the rapid flow (Qd). Finally, the total daily flow (Q) is obtained by combining the slow and fast components, taking into account water exchanges at the watershed level (Perrin et al., 2003 ; Tian et al., 2014). The design of the GR4J model is shown in Figure 2.

$$E_s = \frac{x_1(2 - \frac{s}{x_1}) \tanh(\frac{E_n}{x_1})}{1 + (1 - \frac{s}{x_1}) \tanh(\frac{E_n}{x_1})} \quad (11)$$

Equations (12)–(16) show the Perc as the amount of infiltration, Pr is a part of precipitation (routing store) and, it was divided into two parts (Q1 and Q9) also, Pu is the updated level of production store. Q constitutes 10% of direct runoff, which is obtained through the hydrograph of unit Hu2 with 2 x4 base time [x4 is base time in unit hydrograph UH1 (days)]. The Q9 is another part of 90% of the runoff (delay runoff) which is obtained through the hydrograph of unit Hu1 with X4 base time

$$S_u = s + P_s - E_s \quad (12)$$

$$P_{erc} = S_u \left[1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{4S_u}{9x_1} \right)^4 \right]^{-1/4} \right] \quad (13)$$

$$P_r = P_n - P_s + P_{erc} \quad (14)$$

$$Q_1(i) = 0.1 * \sum_{k=1}^m HU_2(k) * P_r(i - k + 1) \quad (15)$$

$$Q_9(i) = 0.9 * \sum_{k=1}^m HU_1(k) * P_r(i - k + 1) \quad (16)$$

Equation (17) shows F as groundwater exchange and Eqs. (18)–(21) indicate R as the routine moisture storage, Q the final runoff, Qr and Qd runoff in the outlet and direct runoff, respectively (Nayak et al., 2021).

$$F = x_2 \left(\frac{R}{x_3} \right)^{7/2} \quad (17)$$

$$R = \max(0; R + Q_9 + F) \quad (18)$$

$$Q_r = R \left[1 - \left[1 + \left(\frac{R}{x_3} \right)^4 \right]^{-1/4} \right] \quad (19)$$

$$Q_d = \max(0; Q_1 + F) \quad (20)$$

$$Q = Q_r + Q_d \quad (21)$$

where x2 and x3 are the coefficients of groundwater exchange (mm) and the maximum routing store capacity one day ahead (mm), respectively.

✚ Model calibration and validation

Model calibration is a process that modifies the model parameters to adapt them to observed

and simulated values. To calibrate the GR4J model in this study, the four parameters (X1 to X4) listed above were adjusted using the "target value" function in Excel to obtain an accurate correlation between observed and simulated flows for the basin. Calibration was carried out over the period 2016-2018. Validation makes it possible to assess the robustness of the calibration performed, which consists of testing the simulated flows with the parameters obtained during calibration over a validation period independent of the period used for calibration (Klemes, 1986). It was carried out using time series from the period 2019-2022.

✚ GR4J model evaluation criterion

Performance criteria are used to assess the quality of a model's simulations compared to observations. The "objective function" used here is the Nash and Sutcliffe criterion (1970) which is expressed by the equation:

$$\text{NASH} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (Q_{jsim} - Q_{jobs})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (Q_{jobs} - \bar{Q}_{jobs})^2} \quad (22)$$

Q_{jsim} et Q_{jobs} : Are respectively the simulated and observed flow rates at time step

\bar{Q}_{jobs} : is the average of the flow rates observed over the period considered.

In practice, the performance of the model is judged according to the values taken by the NS criterion (Quillat, 2007). The performance of the model can be judged according to the values taken by the Nash criterion:

- **Nash >90%**: the model is excellent;
- **80% < Nash < 90%**: the model is very satisfactory;
- **60% < Nash < 80%**: the model is satisfactory;
- **Nash <60%**: the model is bad

3.2.3 Estimates of surface water flows and stocks

This step involves determining water flows and stocks using the water balance calculation method. The water balance of the catchment area is derived from parameters obtained using NS criteria calculated by flow (Q) applied to floods. This balance concerns the four main components of the water cycle, namely rainfall (P), actual evapotranspiration (ETR), which constitute water flows, and runoff (Q) and infiltration (I), which represent surface and groundwater stocks respectively. It expresses the distribution of precipitation between these components as defined by equation 7.

$$P = Q + ETR + I \quad (23)$$

The amount of water infiltrated (I) is deduced from equation 8 using the formula given in equation 3.

$$I = P - (ETR + Q) \quad (24)$$

ETR is determined by equation 4.

$$ETR = (ETP - En) + Es \quad (25)$$

Where: En: is net evapotranspiration and Es is the amount of evaporation removed from the

production reservoir.

Figure 2 : Methodological framework of the study

4 Results

4.1. Climate change in the me river basin by 2050

4.1.1. Analysis of simulated interannual and seasonal precipitation

Figure 4 shows the variation in average annual precipitation (4A) and the variation in average monthly precipitation (4B) observed and simulated by the MCR and ENSEMBLE models over the reference period (1986-2005) for the assessment of climate model performance in the watershed. First, a comparison was made between simulated and observed annual precipitation totals at the Azaguié station. The EC-EARTH and MPI models overestimate annual rainfall, while the CNRM-CM5 model significantly underestimates it, with interannual rainfall variation well below the interannual variation observed during the reference period (Figure 4(A)).

The seasonal cycle simulated by the MPI, CNRM-CM5 and ENSEMBLE models clearly shows that they tend to underestimate rainfall during the wet season (May to July and October to November) and the dry season from December to April, and to overestimate rainfall during the dry season from August to September. However, the EC-EARTH model only underestimates it during the dry season from December to April. It is important to note that all models, including their average (ENSEMBLE), respect the bimodal nature of the rainfall regime in the study area, but their peak rainfall during the main rainy season occurs later than that observed (Figure 4 (B)).

Figures 4 (E) and 4 (F) below show the impact of correction methods on average annual and monthly precipitation variables over the reference period at the Azaguié station. Analysis of the corrected simulated data makes it possible to evaluate the ability of the selected correction methods to reduce the biases identified for each parameter. The performance of the bias correction is assessed using the percentage bias (PBIAS) with a value between -0.005% and 11.07% after correction (Table III). The closer the value is to 1, the more effective the method is. We observe a distribution of corrected monthly and annual rainfall data in line with that of the observed data, except for the MPI model, which slightly overestimates average annual precipitation. Therefore, all other models correct the average annual precipitation very well. However, the percentage bias after correction is -0.005 for the CNRM-CM5 model, which is very close to 1. This corresponds to the model that best corrects monthly precipitation over the reference period. The linear scaling method used here is effective for model correction.

4.1.2 Analysis of simulated interannual and seasonal temperatures

The interannual temperature variation shown in Figure 4 (C) shows that all models underestimate the temperature except for the CNRM-CM5 model, which presents values very close to the observed values. The MPI-ESM-LR and ENSEMBLE models show interannual variation between +24.5 and 26.5 °C, which is far from the interannual variations in the observed data. The CNRM-CM5 model better simulates the annual temperature variation in the basin, unlike the EC-EARTH model, which deviates significantly, varying between 24.5 and 25.8°C. Thus, interannual variability is more pronounced in the EC-EARTH model than in the other models. The monthly variation observed and simulated by the climate models over the reference period (1986-2005) shown in Figure 4 (D) at the Azaguié station also reflects the bimodal nature of the climate regime. The maximum values are observed in March and November and the minimum values in August. Seasonality is well respected in the different models. However, the different models underestimate the temperature throughout the year except for March and April. The variation in the monthly average temperature for all models is between 25°C and 33°C. The impact of bias correction is similar to that for precipitation.

Table 3 : Statistical analysis of the performance of climate models in simulating mean monthly precipitation in the basin

Models	% BIAS	
	Before correction	After correction
CNRM-CM5	57.68	-0.005
EC-EARTH	9.44	0.24
MPI-ESM-LR	23.13	0.54
TOGETHER	30.08	11.07

Figure 3 : Variation of annual and monthly mean precipitation and temperature of climate models before (AD) and after bias correction (EF)

4.1.3. Potential impacts of climate change on precipitation and temperature in the Mé basin by 2050 according to each climate model

4.1.3.1 Change in precipitation

The results of the time series of the predicted impact of climate change on precipitation in the Mé river basin for scenarios RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 on an annual basis are presented in Figure 5 and the statistics are presented in Table 4. According to both scenarios, all models predict a rainfall deficit over the period 2044 to 2045 and 2053 to 2056, with a value of around 55 mm/year. The rainfall levels predicted under the RCP 4.5 scenario are higher than those predicted under RCP 8.5. According to the RCP4.5 scenario, the CNRM-CM5, MPI-ESM-LR and ENSEMBLE models predict an increase in average annual precipitation with a growth rate of between 0.77% and 7.40%, while EC-EARTH predicts a decrease with a rate of -3.04%. For the RCP8.5 scenario, all models, including ENSEMBLE, predict a slight increase in annual rainfall between 2041 and 2060, with rates of change ranging from 0.24% to 3.43%.

Figure 4 : Comparison between the cumulative annual precipitation corrected over the 2041-2060 horizon under the RCP 4.5 & 8.5 scenarios and the annual precipitation observed over the reference period 1986-2005

Table 4 : Average rate of variation of precipitation simulated by the MCRs over the period 2041-2060

Models	RCP Scenario 4.5	RCP Scenario 8.5
Precipitation increase rate %		
CNRM-CM5	7.4	3.43
EC-EARTH	-3.04	0.52
MPI-ESM-LR	0.96	0.24
TOGETHER	0.77	0.98

4.1.3.2 Temperature change

Figure 6 shows the time series of the projected annual mean temperature over the Mé river basin under the RCP4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios for all climate models. According to both scenarios, all models predicted an increase in the average annual temperature for the future period (2041-2060) ranging from 27 to 28.7 °C (RCP 4.5) and from 27 to 29.5 °C (RCP 8.5), representing an average increase of 0.85°C and 1.25°C respectively, except for the EC-EARTH model, which predicts a

decrease in the average annual temperature in the case of scenario 4.5 to reach 26°C in 2060, representing a decrease of 0.6°C compared to the reference period.

Figure 5 : Variation of corrected annual precipitation over the 2041-2060 horizon under the RCP 4.5 & 8.5 scenarios and the annual precipitation observed over the 1986-2005 reference period

However, on a seasonal basis (Table 5), all models predicted an increase in the average monthly temperature for the future period (2041-2060) for all months except June, July, August and September, where a downward trend ranging from -0.08 °C to -0.01 °C will be observed for all scenarios combined. Thus, all models predict a similar change in average temperature during the long dry season, while a decrease in average temperature is observed during the long rainy season (June and July) and the short dry season (August and September). October and November show the lowest temperatures, while March and April show the highest temperatures.

Table 5: Monthly variation in temperatures simulated by the MCRs under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 for the period 2041-2060 compared to monthly observations over the reference period (1986-2005) at two stations

MONTH	CNRM-CM5		EC-EARTH		MPI-ESM-LR		ENSEMBLE	
	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5	RCP 4.5	RCP 8.5
Jan	0.03	0.09	0	0.07	0.03	0.09	0.02	0.08
Feb	0.16	0.16	0.09	0.13	0.12	0.14	0.12	0.14
Mar	0.2	0.17	0.16	0.15	0.2	0.17	0.19	0.16
Apr	0.18	0.16	0.13	0.12	0.17	0.14	0.16	0.14
May	0.09	0.1	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.07
Jul	-0.01	0.01	-0.08	-0.03	-0.05	-0.02	-0.05	-0.01
Jul	-0.07	-0.04	-0.11	-0.06	-0.08	-0.05	-0.09	-0.05
Aug	-0.08	-0.04	-0.11	-0.06	-0.09	-0.05	-0.09	-0.05
Sep	-0.04	0	-0.1	-0.04	-0.07	-0.03	-0.07	-0.02
Oct	-0.01	0.02	-0.07	-0.02	-0.04	-0.01	-0.04	0
Nov	0.03	0.05	-0.03	0.02	0	0.03	0	0.03
Dec	0	0.06	-0.03	0.04	0.01	0.06	-0.01	0.05

4.2 Results of hydrological modelling

4.2.1 Rainfall-runoff relationship in the catchment area

Analysis of the rainfall-runoff graphs (Figure 7) shows that, over the seven-year period, the rainfall levels observed in 2017 were higher than in the other six years. The rainfall levels observed were 134, 180, 163, 153, 148, 146 and 141 mm for the years 2016 to 2022, respectively. Two major rainfall peaks and a few minor peaks, with a maximum daily value of 260.6 mm, were observed in June 2020. A variation in rainfall was recorded in October and July. From 2016 to 2022, two major rainfall trends emerged, with April, June and July representing the main rainy season and September and November representing the minor rainy season, with rainfall varying from 33 to 260.6 mm/day. However, low rainfall of 0.05 and 50 mm is recorded in January and December (major dry seasons). The recorded flows mirror the rainfall, with two peaks, the first during the major rainy season and the second during the minor rainy season. Flows generally vary according to the amount of rainfall in the basin. Daily flows in the basin vary between 7.08 and 365.10 m³/s. Thus, the data collected during the observation period in the basin show that daily floods are significant, reaching flows of 360 m³/s.

Figure 7. Rainfall-runoff relationship in the Mé basin over the period 2016-2022

4.2.2 Model calibration and validation

The model parameters and performance criteria obtained during calibration and validation over the period 2016-2022 are recorded in Table 6. The years used for model calibration and validation are the periods 2016-2018 and 2019-2022. The Nash performance criterion values are generally satisfactory: 83.1% for calibration and 77% for validation. We observe a variation in the four parameters X1 to X4 between calibration and validation. The production reservoir capacity (X1) varies from 7.40 mm to 8.08 mm, while the underground exchange parameter (X2) is negative (0.31 mm) during calibration and becomes positive during validation (0.35 mm). The one-day capacity of the routing reservoir (X3) varies from 4.88 mm to 4.98 mm for a base time (X4) in the range of 2.18 days to 1.01 days. With these Nash values, the model simulates flood flows well.

Table 6 : Summary of calibrations and validations of the GR4J model

Settings	Periods	X1	X2	X3	X4	NASH (%)
Calibration	2016-2018	7.40	-0.31	4.88	2.18	83.1
Validation	2019-2022	8.08	0.35	4.98	1.01	77

4.2.3 Calculated and simulated hydrographs

Figure 8 shows the observed and simulated hydrographs for the Mé River during calibration (8A) and validation (8B). The graphical results show better synchronism between observed and simulated flows during both calibration and validation. In Figure 8A, low water levels are overestimated for the period 2017-2018. Similarly, the model fails to correctly reproduce low water flows, which are sometimes disrupted by isolated rainfall during dry periods. The correlation between observed flows and flows calculated during calibration (8 C) and validation (8D) shows a good correlation between observed flows and simulated flows during calibration and validation, with respective coefficient of determination values of 85% and 78%.

Figure 8: Calibration and validation of the GR4J model

4.2.4 Estimation of water flows and stocks at the basin outlet

The annual water balance for the period 2016-2022 is shown in Figure 9. Average annual rainfall over the study period is estimated at 1,793.4 mm. Annual rainfall is distributed among the following parameters: actual evapotranspiration (ETR), runoff (Q) and infiltration (I), with respective values of 1,160.26 mm, 435.15 mm and 198 mm in the Mé catchment area. Water flow (evaporation) accounts for 64.69% of precipitation, while runoff and infiltration account for 24.26% and 11.04% respectively, corresponding to surface and underground water storage.

Figure 9: Annual water balance for the period 2016-2022.

Figure 10 shows a graphical representation of the cumulative water storage in the Mé river basin on an annual, monthly and seasonal basis over the period 2016 to 2022. The annual volume of water varies between 1,164 Mm³ and 2,558 Mm³ over the study period. The year 2022 represents the largest water storage with 2,558 Mm³. The largest monthly water storage is obtained in the months of May, June, July, October and November, with values ranging from 232 Mm³ (June) and 640 Mm³ (July), resulting in significant water storage during the short and long rainy seasons. The largest monthly water storage is recorded during the long rainy season (GSP) in 2022 with 1342 Mm³.

Figure 10 : Cumulative water storage in the Mé river basin over the period 2016-2022.

4.3 Potential impacts of climate change on the Mé River by 2050 using the average MCR prediction data used in GR4J

4.3.1 Impact of climate change on water balance terms by 2050.

Based on an analysis of rainfall-runoff graphs for the period 2041-2060 in the Mé watershed, all models predict daily precipitation ranging from 0 to 200 mm. The rainy months remain the same for both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios (May, June, July, October, September and November). However, it predicts a large rainfall peak during the dry season, particularly during the months of December to April, when precipitation reaches 175 mm. The rainfall frequency predicted for the RCP 4.5 scenario is higher than that for the RCP8.5 scenarios. The dark blue curve represents the flows simulated by all models for the year 2050. The variation in flow depends on rainfall (Figure 11). For high intensities above 155 mm, high flows are recorded. In fact, the first rains at the beginning of the season gradually contributed to the saturation of the groundwater table. This leads to very high runoff during intense events. However, the model predicts the highest floods during the month of July (2058 to 2060), with peaks exceeding 5 mm/day for the RCP 4.5 scenario and 2.03 mm/day for the RCP 8.5 scenario during the months of July (2047) and November (2051). The observation of isolated and heavy rainfall is due to the impact of climate change observed in the atmosphere. The hydrological balance calculated over the same period on the Mé river basin shows that ETR is one of the components that has the greatest influence in the river basin, with 78.13% for RCP 4.5 and 81.44% for RCP 8.5, respectively. The second parameter is infiltration, which accounts for 8.79% and 7.80% of precipitation in the Mé basin for RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 respectively. This is the proportion that will be used to recharge the aquifer. The final component of the balance is runoff, which is 13.07% for RCP 4.5 and 10.75% for RCP 8.5. This represents the stock that can be mobilised by 2050 to supply the population.

Figure 11: Rainfall-runoff relationship and water balance for 2050

4.3.2. Potential impacts of climate change on the flow rates of the Mé River: changes in annual and seasonal flow rates

Figure 12 shows the seasonal evolution of cumulative flow in the Mé River by 2050 according to the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios compared to flows observed during the reference period (2016–2022). According to both scenarios, we will see a disruption in the hydrological regime in terms of seasonal flow patterns and the date of peak floods. Major floods will occur from July to November. Peak floods will now occur in November instead of June and July, as was the case in the past (2016-2022). This situation means that the seasons could shift in the 21st century. Furthermore, for the RCP4.5 scenario, the years 2048, 2049, 2055 and 2056 will see a significant decrease in annual flow, with respective values of 68 m³/s, 833 m³ /s, 72 m³ /s, 2735 m³ /s, equivalent to annual water storage of 5.9 Mm³, 71 Mm³, 6 Mm³ and 236 Mm³ respectively. This observation is also expected in terms of flows according to the RCP 8.5 scenario during the years 2048, 2055 and 2056, with respective values of 52 m³/s, 48 m³/s, 463 m³ /s, representing annual water volumes of 4.5 Mm³, 4 Mm³ and 40 Mm³ respectively.

The RCP 4.5 scenario predicts a 28% decrease in the flow of the Mé during the long dry season (December to April) and a 77% decrease during the long rainy season (May to July). The RCP 8.5 scenario predicts a 35% decrease in flow during the dry season (December to April). It also predicts an 85% decrease in the flow of the Mé during the rainy season (May to July). Both scenarios predict a more significant increase in flow (over 60%) in September during the short dry season and a slight increase in flow (over 20%) in October and November during the short rainy season. The flow of the Mé would decrease by an average of 63.35% in the RCP 4.5 scenario and would also decrease by an average of 71% in the RCP 8.5 scenario.

Figure 12: Change in annual cumulative water volume and seasonal flow according to the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios

5. Discussion

The results of compiling data using the GR4J model for the period 2016-2022 yielded satisfactory Nash-Sutcliffe (NS) criteria in calibration and validation, with respective values of 83.1% and 77%. These values corroborate those obtained by Dao et al. (2019) and Delaigue et al. (2017). During their work, the latter obtained Nash values between 75% and 78% for calibration and validation respectively with the same GR6J. All these results are consistent with those obtained by several authors (Perrin, 2000 ; Ouédraogo, 2001 ; Ardoin, 2004 ; Sighomnou, 2004 ; Kouassi, 2007 ; Kouakou et al., 2007 ; Mangoua, 2013), who showed a deterioration in NS values when moving from calibration to validation. These poor performances of the model in validation can be attributed to the length of the calibration and validation period. The result obtained by Marie-Rosine et al. (2020) show that the best calibration and validation period for the GR4J model is six years. Furthermore, general observation of the hydrographs has shown small differences between the simulated and observed hydrographs for low water flows. These shifts (delays) in the simulated hydrograph flows could be explained in large part by the impact of climate change (Dao et al., 2019) and the failure to take into account the surface conditions (by the GR4J model) of the watershed, where the degradation of the vegetation cover is highlighted (Kone, 2023), Meddi M and Belhadj BF (2019), Mangoua (2013). The water balance calculated

for the period 2016-2022 shows that ETR is the dominant parameter in the water cycle, accounting for 64.2% of precipitation. This high rate appears to be favoured by global warming and by vegetation cover dominated by degraded forests, fallow land and crop fields. Next, surface runoff accounts for around 24.5% of average precipitation in the basin, representing a water stock of 2558Mm³ that can be used to supply drinking water to the population. This result is comparable to that obtained by Koffi et al. (2014) using the same model on the Bété and Djibi watersheds, with respective runoff rates of 20% and 26%. These high runoff values can be explained by the degradation of vegetation cover and the rapid urbanisation of the Mé watershed, as indicated by Traoré (2016). Finally, the infiltrated layer represents 11.3% of rainfall. This infiltration value confirms the results obtained by Bamory et al (2017), Kouakou (2011), Yao (2015), Kouassi (2007) and Hughes (2004), which indicate that infiltration generally accounts for between 10% and 30% of precipitation. It represents the proportion likely to feed the aquifers. This difference between runoff and infiltration could be linked to soil sealing due to the severe degradation of vegetation cover in favour of habitats and crops in the catchment area. Analysis of the simulated raw data revealed biases related to these factors. Several studies have shown that regional climate model (RCM) outputs cannot be used directly as inputs for impact models due to the systematic biases they contain (Piani et al., 2010, Hagemann et al., 2011, Kaboré et al., 2015). This analysis showed satisfactory reproduction of the seasonality and bimodal precipitation regime by the three models MPI-ESM-LR, EC-EARTH, CNRM-CM5 and ENSEMBLE. All models overestimate both monthly average and annual precipitation data, with the exception of the CNRM-CM5 and ENSEMBLE models, which underestimate them. On the other hand, monthly temperatures are under estimated by the various models throughout the year except during March and April. The annual temperature is underestimated by the MPI-ESM-LR, EC-EARTH and ENSEMBLE models and slightly overestimated by the CNRM-CM5 model. The corrections made have thus considerably reduced the bias rates of the various models in the distribution of the different parameters before their use in the study of the impact of climate change. A comparative analysis of these corrected future data (2041-2060) forced by the three MCRs with historical data observed at the Azaguié station in the Mé watershed over the period 1986-2005 shows various trends. The models predict a slight increase in average annual precipitation of 7.4% (CRNM), 0.96% (MPI) and 0.77% (ENSEMBLE) according to the RCP4.5 scenarios and 3.43%, 0.24% and 0.98% respectively according to the RCP 8.5 scenario. Projections made by ROUDIER (2012), IPCC (2013) and G. PANTHOU (2013) in West Africa confirm the same trends, particularly the increase in precipitation over the periods 2031-2050 and 2071-2090. According to Kpan et al. (2021), this would mean that the rainfall recovery experienced in recent years could see a positive trend in the coming years. This upward trend in rainfall is at odds with the findings of several authors who predict a rainfall deficit in West Africa in the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios for the Senegal and Bandama river basins respectively (Mbaye et al., 2015) and (Soro et al., 2017). Furthermore, the work of (Koua, 2014) revealed a decrease in precipitation of 10.27% by 2050 and 14.90% by 2080 in the Buyo Dam watershed (Côte d'Ivoire) using the SWAT model and the UKMO-HadGEM1 model according to scenario A1B. Furthermore, based on the MCR prediction results, the general trend in temperature change observed in the study area indicates an increase of 0.85°C to 1.25°C by 2050. Our results corroborate those of KPAN et al (2021), who predicted an estimated temperature increase of between 1.20°C (SRA1B) and 1.29°C (SRA2) over the period 2015 to 2050 compared to the 1963-2014 period, and those of OGA et al (2016) and DANUMAH (2016), who predict a temperature rise of 1.29°C and 0.32 to 1.36°C respectively by 2050 in the same south-eastern coastal area of Côte d'Ivoire. This increase in temperature could explain the rate of change in

ETR predicted by the ENSEMBLE of MCRs following the assessment of the terms of the water balance, with 78.13% for RCP 4.5 compared to 81.44% for RCP 8.5. Given the evolution of these variables (rainfall, temperature and ETR), we can expect the flow of the Mé River to be impacted by the slight increase in precipitation, the increase in temperature and the increase in ETR. This justifies the decrease in the runoff rate to 13.07% for RCP 4.5 and 10.75% for RCP 8.5 of the predicted precipitation (1313 mm and 1261 mm respectively). These runoff values are significantly lower than those obtained for the 2016-2022 period (24.5% of precipitation). Thus, according to the RCP 4.5 scenario, the ENSEMBLE of MCRs predicts a 28% decrease in the flow of the Mé during the long dry season (December to April) and a 77% decrease during the long rainy season (May to July). As for the RCP 8.5 scenario, it predicts a 35% decrease in flow during the dry season (December to April). It also predicts an 85% decrease in the flow of the Mé during the rainy season (May to July). Both scenarios predict a more significant increase in flow (over 60%) in September during the short dry season and a slight increase in flow (over 20%) in October and November during the short rainy season. Finally, the flow of the Mé would decrease by an average of 63.35% in the RCP 4.5 scenario and by an average of 71% in the RCP 8.5 scenario. These results are consistent with those obtained by N'dri et al (2019) on the estimated impact of climate change on the water resources of the Aghien lagoon. They predict a 42% decrease in the lagoon's flow during the long dry season (December to April) and a 57% decrease during the long rainy season (May to July) according to the RCP 4.5 scenario. As for the RCP 8.5 scenario, it predicts a 44% decrease in flow during the dry season (December to April) and a 64% decrease during the rainy season. According to this author, the flow of the Aghien lagoon would decrease by an average of 9.42% in the RCP 4.5 scenario and by an average of 18.24% in the RCP 8.5 scenario. These results are consistent with those of Ardoin-Bardin (2004) in the Senegal, Gambia and Sassandra river basins, Biao (2017) in the Ouémé river basin in Benin (West Africa), Koua (2014) in the Buyo dam watershed, and Kouakou et al. (2012) in the Comoé River watershed. Their results predict a decrease in river flows in these different basins of up to approximately 20% under the influence of climate change.

6. Conclusion

The aim of this study is to assess the future impact of climate change on water resources in the Mé region in order to simulate runoff and evaluate water stocks using the hydrological balance for the period 2041-2060. Three climate models (CNRM, MPI and EC-EARTH) from the CORDEX-AFRICA project and their Ensemble according to the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios were used to assess the impact of climate change. The GR4J hydrological model is used to simulate hydrological processes in the Mé river basin. The calibration and validation results for the Mé basin showed that the model performs well in simulating future changes in ETP, precipitation and river flow in the Mé River in a context of climate change.

Indeed, the model outputs gave globally satisfactory Nash (NS) values in calibration and validation, with respective values of 83.1% and 77%. High urbanisation coupled with anthropogenic activities has a retroactive effect on rainfall, with the result that flows tend to decrease on the Mé, with 24.26% of precipitation corresponding to 2558 Mm³ as water storage recorded in the catchment area during the study period. The calculated and observed hydrographs show good similarities between them over the calibration and validation period. The hydrological balance of the Mé watershed showed that 64.2% of the average annual rainfall estimated at 1793.4 mm on the Mé evaporated (water flow). The proportion of water runoff is 24.94% and 11.3% for infiltrated water, constituting surface water and groundwater stocks respectively. This model can therefore be used as a basis for estimating water flows and stocks in the basin. The results indicate a future temperature increase of between 0.85°C and 1.25°C by 2050, while precipitation is expected to increase by an average of more than 7.4% (CRNM), 0.96% (MPI) and 0.77%

(ENSEMBLE) according to the RCP4.5 scenarios, and by 3.43%, 0.24% and 0.98% respectively according to the RCP 8.5 scenario. As with precipitation, the annual flow of the Mé would decrease in both RCP scenarios. The annual flow is expected to decrease by an average of 65.35% according to RCP 4.5 and by more than 71% according to RCP 8.5. The scenarios also predict a decrease in the seasonal flow of the Mé River. According to the RCP 4.5 scenario, a 28% decrease in flow during the dry season (December to April) and a 77% decrease during the wet season (July to May) is predicted. According to the RCP 8.5 scenario, a 35% decrease in flow during the dry season and an 85% decrease during the wet season is expected. However, flow is expected to increase by more than 60% in September (dry season) and more than 20% in November (wet season) by 2050. It should be borne in mind that this is a model that uses a hydrological model and the average of three climate models, which involve uncertainties. The results of this study are only projections of two possible and equally probable futures scenarios for 2050. Taking into account the potential impact of climate change on the future evolution of the Mé will therefore strengthen the policy for the development and management of this water resource, which will need to be adjusted according to observed or foreseeable uses.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, A.F., A.D. and E.S.K.; Methodology, A.F., A.D., and E.S.K. ; Software, A.F. and E.S.K.; Validation, E.S.K., A.D. and B.K., formal analysis, A.F., E.S.K and A.D.; Investigation, E.S.K. and A.D., Data curation, E.S.K. and A.D., Writing—original draft preparation, A.D.; Writing-review and editing, A.F., A.D., E.S.K., D.L.G. and B.K., Visualization, A.F., A.D., E.S.K., B.K. and D.L.G., Project administration, A.D.; Funding acquisition, A.D., E.S.K, and A.F. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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